

International Journal of Case Reports (ISSN:2572-8776)

Acute Coronary syndrome in a patient newly diagnosed with Charcot-Marie-Tooth Neuropathy: a review of cardiovascular disease in this inherited neuropathy

Garrick Edouard Laudin¹, Thomas De Beenhouwer²

¹Department of Internal medicine: Kalafong Provincial Tertiary Hospital (University of Pretoria), University of Pretoria – Department of Internal Medicine, Kalafong Provincial Tertiary Hospital (Klinikala Building); 1 Klipspringer Street, Atteridgeville, Pretoria (South Africa), 0008

²Department of Cardiology: Steve Biko Academic Hospital (University of Pretoria)

ABSTRACT

Whilst we suspect that there is no clear association between the two major diagnoses we made in this patient during this hospitalisation (i.e. coronary artery disease and CMT neuropathy), the literature from a series of published case reports does perhaps show an association between CMT and abnormalities of cardiac conduction.

Brief Summary:

This case reports follows the occurrence of an antero-lateral ST segment elevation myocardial infarction in a 34-year-old male newly diagnosed with an inherited neuropathy in the form of Charcot-Marie-Tooth type 1A.

Keywords: Acute Coronary syndrome, Charcot-Marie-Tooth Neuropathy, cardiovascular disease

*Correspondence to Author:

Garrick Edouard Laudin
Department of Internal medicine:
Kalafong Provincial Tertiary Hospital (University of Pretoria), University of Pretoria – Department of Internal Medicine, Kalafong Provincial Tertiary Hospital (Klinikala Building); 1 Klipspringer Street, Atteridgeville, Pretoria (South Africa), 0008

How to cite this article:

Garrick Edouard Laudin, Thomas De Beenhouwer. Acute Coronary syndrome in a patient newly diagnosed with Charcot-Marie-Tooth Neuropathy: a review of cardiovascular disease in this inherited neuropathy. International Journal of Case Reports, 2019 4:83.

eSciPub LLC, Houston, TX USA.
Website: <http://escipub.com/>

Case Report

Mr RP is a 34-year-old male who presented to the emergency department at our facility with a primary complaint of acute-onset (5 hour) central chest pain with radiation to the left arm.

Initial electrocardiogram demonstrated an antero-lateral ST segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) and a lytic in the form of alteplase was administered in the emergency department with clinical and electrocardiographic improvement.

Patient was initiated on aspirin/ clopidogrel/ heparin/ statin and was transferred to the

coronary care unit, where there were no hemodynamic or electrical complications noted. The peak level of his troponin I reached 15472 ng/L (table one) at day 2 and a transthoracic echocardiography revealed mild left ventricular systolic dysfunction with apical hypokinesia and a small thrombus. Therefore, he was initiated on warfarin and the ASA was stopped.

His risk factors for coronary artery disease were a positive family history of ischemic heart disease as well as a seven pack-year history of smoking.

Figure 1 : Electrocardiogram performed on day 2 (trop level 15472 ng/L) post admission, as the initial ECG at the emergency department could not be located

Figure 2: X-Ray of the right foot demonstrating pes cavus and a “claw toe” deformity

Table 1: Laboratory results at baseline

Laboratory parameter	Value	Laboratory Normal Value
Full blood count		
White cell count (x10 ⁹ /L)	23.39 (H)	3.92 – 10.40
Haemoglobin (g/dL)	15.6	13.4 – 17.5
Hematocrit (L/L)	0.476	0.390 – 0.510
Mean Cell Volume (fL)	85.6	83.1 – 101.6
Mean Cell Hemoglobin (pg)	28.1	27.8 – 34.8
Red cell distribution width (%)	14.3	12.1-16..3
Platelet count (x10 ⁹ /L)	523	171 - 388
Urea and Creatinine	Normal	
Calcium, Magnesium, Phosphate	Normal	
Cardiac Markers		
Creatine kinase MB mass (ug/L)	144.40 (H)	- 5.20
Myoglobin (ug/L)	88.7	<154.9
Creatine Kinase (CK) (U/L)	1081 (H)	20 – 200
Troponin I (ng/L) (Rule in ACS: >300)	15472 (H)	
Limited Liver function		
Alanine transaminase (ALT) (U/L)	54 (H)	10 – 40
Aspartate transaminase (AST) (U/L)	151 (H)	15 – 40
Lipogram and Metabolic profile		
Total Cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.52	
Triglyceride (mmol/L)	1.49	
High-density lipoprotein (mmol/L)	1.04	
Low-density lipoprotein (mmol/L)	2.91	
Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (mIU/L)	1.13	0.35 - 4.94
Thyroxine/ Free-T4 (pmol/L)	18.6	9.0 - 19.0

Further questioning of our patient revealed a family history of suspected undiagnosed neuromuscular disease. Our patient revealed that members of his family member have had abnormalities of their feet as well as abnormal gait. Our patient also revealed multiple previous surgeries to his right foot – see figure two. Musculoskeletal and neurological examination of Mr RP revealed distal muscle weakness (difficulty with shirt buttoning) as well as wasting of the intrinsic muscles of the hands. Mr RP also demonstrated a bilateral foot drop with a high steppage gait.

The neurology service at our facility was consulted with a tentative diagnosis of a hereditary neuropathy in the form of Charcot-Marie-Tooth neuropathy with a view to a positive

genetic diagnosis as well as nerve conduction studies.

Coronary angiogram was performed and revealed no significant coronary artery disease. There was a mild lesion noted in the proximal LAD with good TIMI 3 flow distally. We did not perform intravascular imaging, but this lesion was suspected to be the culprit. An LV angiogram was performed and revealed a good systolic function with some apical hypokinesia. No thrombus was demonstrated at this point.

A nuclear sestamibi scan was done and revealed a small transmural fixed perfusion defect involving the apical inferior wall with no associated stress-induced ischemia (figure 4). The decision was made for conservative medical therapy.

Figure 3: coronary angiography with two views of the LAD (top) and two views of the RCA (bottom)

Figure 4: Cardiac Sestamibi scan

Figure 5: Nerve conduction studies (motor component)

Nerve conduction studies demonstrated a mixed motor/sensory neuropathy (predominantly axonal) involving the upper and lower limbs (figure 5). Genetic studies demonstrated positivity for a heterozygous duplication of chromosome 17p12 in keeping with Charcot-Marie-Tooth type 1A disease.

Discussion

Charcot-Marie-Tooth neuropathy type 1 (CMT1), also known by the name peroneal muscle atrophy (PMA), is a demyelinating peripheral neuropathy characterized by distal muscle weakness with associated muscle atrophy. Distal sensory loss as well as delayed velocities on nerve conduction studies are also some hallmarks of this disease¹.

CMT is slowly progressive and abnormalities of the feet include a pes cavus deformity and may also result in bilateral foot drop. Affected individuals usually become symptomatic between the ages of five and 25¹.

The inheritance pattern of CMT1 is autosomal dominant with more than sixty percent of patients having inherited the *PMP22* duplication¹.

Our patient has all of these findings and the diagnosis of CMT could be confirmed.

Those neuromuscular diseases typically associated with cardiac involvement include diseases with multi-system manifestations like

mitochondrial myopathies as well as myotonic dystrophies. Neuromuscular disorders primarily affecting neuronal transmission are less likely to be associated with cardiac involvement as compared to myopathies².

Prospective studies from the US in the 1970's by Isner *et al* analysed various cardiac parameters in a cohort of 68 patients with CMT disease and in this cohort, they concluded that cardiac abnormalities in patients with Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease were simply a chance occurrence in a patient subset with a rare disease entity.

Literature searches on the association between Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease and heart disease in adult patient was conducted using Pubmed and revealed 46 search results whilst a similar search on Medline provided 27 search results. A search on the Cochrane database with the same search terms produced 6 results with none applicable to this case report topic. A summary of reported cases from these searches that demonstrated applicability to cardiac disease in adults with CMT can be found in table 2 below. The differentiation between the different types of CMT were not always delineated from the case reports that were included in table two below. The presence of coronary artery disease demonstrated by coronary angiography or post mortem studies was demonstrated in 4 of the 21 published case report articles. Of the 21 published case reports found in the literature,

Table 2: Case reports of CMT patients with cardiac disease

Author and year of journal publication	Patient Age/Gender	ECG	Echocardiogram/ Cardiac catheterization	Coronary Angiography
Leak (1961) ³	59 M	Atrial flutter	-	-
Combrink, Davis, Snyman (1962) (mentioned in Littler 1970) ⁴	Age unknown, F	Right bundle branch block (RBBB)	-	-
Gazes , Culer , Taber, Kelly (1965) (mentioned in Littler 1970) ⁴	3 family members	RBBB	-	-
Littler (1970) ⁴	42 M	Complete heart block	-	-
Ponder, Chatterjee, Sutton (1971) ⁵	49 M	Atrial fibrillation and complete AV block	Elevation of right ventricular (RV) systolic pressure & wide pulmonary artery (PA) pressure	Normal .
	57 M	Atrial flutter, with complete AV block	-	-
Kay, Littler, Meade (1972) ⁶		RBBB	-	-
Isner, Hawley, Weintraub, Engel (1979) ⁷		5 patients in cohort demonstrated conduction abnormalities	17 patients in cohort had mitral valve prolapse	-
Lowry, Littler (1983) ⁸	54 M	Atrial fibrillation	Echo: normal	-
	27 M	Junctional escape rhythm with complete absence of atrial activity	Cath: Dilated left ventricle (LV)	Normal
Martin-Du Pan RC, Juge C, Perrenoud JJ (1984) ⁹	-	-	Cardiomyopathy	-
Roelofse , Shipton (1985) ¹⁰	44 F	Sick Sinus Syndrome	-	-
Rosselot, Brinck (1989) ¹¹	57 (unknown)	Complete AV block	-	-
Yoshida <i>et al</i> (1991) ¹²	70 M	-	Post-mortem: Dilated Cardiomyopathy	PM: intimal atheromatous thickening
Tanaka, Tsuchida, Namiki (1994) ¹³	24 F	Second degree atrioventricular (AV) block	Echo: mitral valve prolapse	-
Sevillano Fernández <i>et al</i> (1994) ¹⁴	Two males (age unknown)	-	Echo: dilated cardiomyopathy	-
Rubinstein, Moghe, Mizrahi, Dissin (2004) ¹⁵	41 F	ventricular fibrillation	-	Normal
Erentuğ, Bozbuğa, Akinci, Yakut (2004) ¹⁶	36 M	Anterior wall ischemia with sinus rhythm	-	Left main 60% occlusion, triple vessel disease
Corrado <i>et al</i> (2006) ¹⁷	50 F	LBBB	Echo: left Ventricular Hypertrabeculation/ Noncompaction	-
Shankar <i>et al</i> (2007) ¹⁸	57 M	-	-	Triple vessel disease
Bui, Marco (2008) ¹⁹	59 F	-	Adenosine stress test: hyperdynamic left ventricle (ejection fraction of 80%)	Nonobstructive coronary artery disease
Liang, Grogan, Ackerman, Goodsell (2016) ²⁰	51F	polymorphic VT (initial)	Arrhythmogenic right ventricular cardiomyopathy	
Abdul, Schneider, Cetta, Driscoll (2018) ²¹	25 F	-	Cath: elevated right atrial pressure; echo: patent cavopulmonary anastomosis & dilated right atrium (RA)	-

A.Flutter (Atrial Flutter), AV (atrioventricular), Cath (cardiac catheterization), echo (echocardiogram), ECG (electrocardiogram), EF (ejection fraction), F (female), LBBB (left bundle branch block), M (male), Mitral Valve Prolapse (MVP), PM (post-mortem), RBBB (right bundle branch block)

more than 70% of the case reports of patients with CMT had an abnormal electrocardiogram with 14 of the 21 case reports alluding to ECGs with conduction abnormalities.

We suspect that there is no clear association between the two major diagnoses we made in this patient during this hospitalisation (i.e. coronary artery disease and CMT neuropathy).

Although our patient did not have a conduction abnormality, the literature from a series of published case reports does perhaps show an association between CMT and abnormalities of cardiac conduction.

Upon discharge our patient was advised to quit smoking and to continue his best medical therapy. He was also referred for physical and occupational therapy and for further genetic counselling. **Conclusion:**

Whilst there appears to be no clear data to suggest a clear association between coronary artery disease and inherited neuropathies in the form of Charcot-Marie-tooth neuropathy, prior case reports do suggest that there may be an association between this neuropathy and disorders of cardiac conduction.

Abbreviations

Charcot-Marie-Tooth (CMT), High-density lipoprotein (HDL), Low-density lipoprotein (LDL), Tc99m-MIBI (Technetium (99mTc) sestamibi, PMA (peroneal muscle atrophy)

Acknowledgements

University of Pretoria Department of Cardiology (Dr Brits), University of Pretoria Department of Radiology, University of Pretoria Department of Nuclear Medicine (Dr Ismaheel Lawal, Dr Honest Ndlovu), University of Pretoria Department of Neurology (Prof M. Kakaza, Dr M. Pillay), University of Pretoria Department of Psychiatry (Dr MNM. Morwe), National Health Laboratory Service (Braamfontein Human Genetics Unit – Dr FB Essop)

Funding Sources

Nil

Disclosures

Nil

Declaration:

1. All authors have participated in the work and have reviewed and agree with the content of the article.
2. None of the article contents are under consideration for publication in any other journal or have been published in any journal.
3. No portion of the text has been copied from other material in the literature (unless in quotation marks, with citation).
4. I am aware that it is the author's responsibility to obtain permission for any figures or tables reproduced from any prior publications, and to cover fully any costs involved. Such permission must be obtained prior to final acceptance

References

1. Bird TD. Charcot-Marie-Tooth Neuropathy Type 1. 1998 Aug 31 [Updated 2015 Mar 26]. In: Adam MP, Ardinger HH, Pagon RA, et al., editors. GeneReviews® [Internet]. Seattle (WA): University of Washington, Seattle; 1993-2019. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1205/>
2. Finsterer J, Stöllberger C. Heart Disease in Disorders of Muscle, Neuromuscular Transmission, and the Nerves. *Korean Circulation Journal*. 2016;46(2): <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4805555/pdf/kcj-46-117.pdf> (accessed 27 May 2019).
3. Leak D. Paroxysmal atrial flutter in peroneal muscular atrophy. *Br Heart J* 1961; 23(): <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1017773/> (accessed 09 June 2019).
4. Littler WA. Heart block and peroneal muscular atrophy. A family study. *Q J Med* 1970; 39(155): <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/5478510> (accessed 09 June 2019).
5. Ponder BA, Chatterjee K, Sutton GC. Complete heart block in patients with peroneal muscular atrophy. *Postgrad Med J*. 1971; 47(551): <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/5098917> (accessed 09 June 2019)
6. Kay JM, Littler WA, Meade JB. Ultrastructure of myocardium in familial heart block and peroneal muscular atrophy. 1972;34(10): <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/5086979> (accessed 09 June 2019).
7. Isner JM, Hawley RJ, Weintraub AM, Engel WK. Cardiac Findings in Charcot-Marie-Tooth

- Disease. *Archives of Internal Medicine* 1979; 139(1161-1165).
<https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jamainternalmedicine/article-abstract/599264> (accessed 27 May 2019).
8. Lowry PJ, Littler WA. Peroneal muscular atrophy associated with cardiac conducting tissue disease: further observations. *Postgrad Med J* 1983;59(694):
<https://pmj.bmj.com/content/59/694/530.long> (accessed 09 June 2019).
 9. Martin-Du Pan RC, Juge C, Perrenoud JJ. Congestive cardiomyopathy and pyruvate elevation in a case of Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease. *Schweiz Med Wochenschr.* 1984; 114(18):.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/6539500> (accessed 11 June 2019).
 10. Roelofse JA, Shipton EA. Anaesthesia for abdominal hysterectomy in Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease. A case report.. *S Afr Med J* 1985; 67(15):
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/3983744> (accessed 11 June 2019)
 11. Rosselot E, Brinck G. Conduction system disease and Charcot-Marie-Tooth syndrome. *Rev Med Chil* 1989;117(8):
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/2519453> (accessed 09 June 2019).
 12. Yoshida H, Inagaki M, Shukuya M, Ono S, Shimizu N, Doba N, Shimizu N, Sugano I, Nagao K. Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease associated with dilated cardiomyopathy: an autopsy case report. *Kokyu To Junkan* 1991; 39(3):
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/2047612> (accessed 09 June 2019).
 13. Tanaka S, Tsuchida H, Namiki A. Epidural anesthesia for a patient with Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease, mitral valve prolapse syndrome and IInd degree AV block. *Masui* 1994; 43(6):
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/8072157> (accessed 09 June 2019).
 14. Sevillano Fernández JA, Paz Fraile A, Cano Ballesteros JC, Villalba García MV, Otero Pérez R, Gilsanz Fernández C. Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease, dilated myocardopathy and cardiac conduction disorders. *An Med Interna* 1994; 11(9):.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/7858092> (accessed 09 June 2019).
 15. Rubinstein J, Moghe R, Mizrachi A, Dissin J. Triptan use preceding life-threatening arrhythmias in charcot-marie-tooth: a case report and review of the literature. *Clin Neuropharmacol* 2004; 27(1):
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/15090931> (accessed 09 June 2019).
 16. Erentuğ V, Bozbuğa N, Akinci E, Yakut C. Charcot-Marie-Tooth syndrome and surgical management for left main coronary artery disease. *J Card Surg* 2004; 19(3):
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/15151653> (accessed 09 June 2019).
 17. Corrado G, Checcarelli N, Santarone M, Stollberger C, Finsterer J. Left ventricular hypertrabeculation/noncompaction with PMP22 duplication-based Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease type 1A. *Cardiology* 2006; 105(3):
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/16449811> (accessed 09 June 2019).
 18. Shankar V, Markan S, Gandhi SD, Iqbal Z, Novalija J, Nicolosi AC et al. Perioperative Implications of Charcot-Marie-Tooth Disease During Coronary Artery Bypass Graft Surgery. *J Cardiothorac Vasc Anesth* 2007; 21(4):
[https://www.jcvaonline.com/article/S1053-0770\(06\)00324-7/pdf](https://www.jcvaonline.com/article/S1053-0770(06)00324-7/pdf) (accessed 09 June 2019).
 19. Bui AH, Marco AP. Peripheral nerve blockade in a patient with Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease. *Can J Anaesth* 2008;55(10):
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/BF03017751#citeas> (accessed 09 June 2019).
 20. Liang JJ, Grogan M, Ackerman MJ, Goodsell K. LMNA-Mediated Arrhythmogenic Right Ventricular Cardiomyopathy and Charcot-Marie-Tooth Type 2B1: A Patient-Discovered Unifying Diagnosis. 2016;27(7):
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/jc.12984> (accessed 11 June 2019).
 21. Abdul TY, Schneider AE, Cetta F, Driscoll DJ. Fontan Failure Secondary to Charcot-Marie-Tooth-Induced Phrenic Neuropathy. *Tex Heart Inst J* 2018; 45(4):
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6183634/> (accessed 09 June 2019).

